

SCHOOL OF NURSING GRADUATION PROJECT (SoN GP)

SYNOPSIS

Fall Semester
2023-2024

Foreword

It is with great pride that we present the **School of Nursing Graduation Project (SoN GP) Synopses** for Fall Semester 2023-2024, a remarkable collection of research endeavors showcasing the creativity, dedication, and intellectual curiosity of our undergraduate nursing students. This compilation highlights diverse topics in nursing and health, reflecting the students' commitment to addressing contemporary challenges in healthcare. Under the expert guidance of our faculty, these projects exemplify the integration of research and evidence-based practice, key skills essential for professional success. The Graduation Project course is designed to cultivate critical thinking, foster innovation, and prepare our students to excel in the dynamic and demanding healthcare environment.

Table of Contents

Cover Page

Foreword

SELF REPORTED MENSTRUAL CHANGES FOLLOWING COVID-19 VACCINATION IN THE GOVERNORATE OF AL-DAKHILIYAH, OMAN **6**

Asia Saif Salim Al Mahrouqi

Asmahan Awadh Musallam Qasboob

Ms. Pelagia Paastor de Polonia

DEPRESSION AND HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG PATIENTS WITH TYPE-2 DIABETES MELLITUS ATTENDING PRIMARY DIABETIC CENTER IN SOUTH SHARQIYA **7**

Amira Ali Juma Al Shaibi

Dr. Oscar M. Turingan

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE ON PREVENTION OF CENTRAL LINE-ASSOCIATED BLOODSTREAM INFECTION (CLABSI) AMONG ONCOLOGY AND MEDICAL STAFF NURSES AT ROYAL HOSPITAL, OMAN **8**

Ilham Mansoor Alfarsi

Dr. Oscar M. Turingan

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVANT LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG NURSES OF SULTAN QABOOS HOSPITAL, SALALAH **9**

Tariq Ramis Salim Jaboob

Abdul-Aziz Abdullah Ali-Suliman

Dr. Oscar M. Turingan

OMANI FAMILY CARE PROVIDERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS OLDER PEOPLE AND THEIR PERCEPTION TOWARDS DAY CARE CENTER FOR ELDERLY PEOPLE IN OMAN **10**

Humaid Mohammed Al-Masoudi

Dr. Oscar M. Turingan

FACTORS AFFECTING THE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF PREGNANT WOMEN TOWARD ANTENATAL CARE IN ALMAWALEH HEALTH CENTER, A'SEEB, MUSCAT GOVERNORATE **11**

Kadhiya Al Riyami

Ms. Dulce Racquel M. Javier

Table of Contents

OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURES TO BLOOD AND BLOOD PRODUCTS: ASSESSING KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES AMONG HEALTHCARE PERSONNEL OF THE ACCIDENT AND EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT OF KHOULA HOSPITAL, OMAN	12
Said Mohammed Abdullah Al Rashdi Naif Rabia Ali Al Ghafri Dr. Oscar M. Turingan	
THE LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF CLIENTS ATTENDING PRIMARY HEALTH CARE FACILITIES IN WILAYAT NIZWA ON THE HEALTH CARE DELIVERY SERVICES IN THE SULTANATE OF OMAN	13
Ahood Mohammed Mubarak Al Nadabi Saeeda Said Hamed Al Rawahi Mr. Phildon Jonar M. Austria	
KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF CAREGIVERS ON PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION AMONG BED-RIDDEN CLIENTS IN MUSCAT	14
Safiya Saif Said Al-Harthy Mr. Phildon Jonar M. Austria	
JOB SATISFACTION AND TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG NURSES WORKING IN EMERGENCY AND IN-PATIENT DEPARTMENTS IN SULTAN QABOOS HOSPITAL, SALALAH	15
Salma Ramahan Jamaan Bait Nasib Dr. Jestoni Maniago	

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	SELF REPORTED MENSTRUAL CHANGES FOLLOWING COVID-19 VACCINATION IN THE GOVERNORATE OF AL-DAKHILIYAH, OMAN
Student(s)	Asia Saif Salim Al Mahrouqi Asmahan Awadh Musallam Qasboob
Supervisor(s)	Ms. Pelagia Paastor de Polonia
Problem Statement	The spread of the COVID-19 virus affected people worldwide in many profound ways, prompting a rapid global vaccination effort. Various vaccines, including Pfizer, AstraZeneca, and Ad26.COV.2.S., were developed. While numerous studies have focused on the vaccine's impact on general health, few have examined its effect on the menstrual cycle.
Significance of the Study	This study will assist the Ministry of Health, healthcare providers, and vaccine manufacturers in understanding menstrual changes post-vaccination, contributing to informed healthcare decisions.
Aim of the Study	The primary goal is to assess perceived menstrual changes following COVID-19 vaccination. The study will focus on women aged 18 and older in Al-Dakhiliyah Governorate, Oman, aiming to determine the prevalence of menstrual irregularities and the relationship between these changes and the COVID-19 vaccine.
Methodology	This quantitative, cross-sectional study will collect data on menstrual cycle changes using self-administered online surveys. Data will be gathered from women over 18 in Al-Dakhiliyah Governorate. Previous studies, such as those by Salualeh et al. (2022) and Muhaidat et al. (2022), have used similar methodologies to investigate the prevalence of menstrual irregularities post-vaccination.
Overall Outcome	The study will examine the impact of the COVID-19 vaccine on women aged 18-45 in Al-Dakhiliyah Governorate. Preliminary results indicate that many participants experienced changes in cycle duration, flow patterns, and other symptoms such as intermittent bleeding.
Keywords	<i>COVID-19 vaccine, menstrual cycle, menstrual irregularities, cross-sectional study</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	DEPRESSION AND HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG PATIENTS WITH TYPE-2 DIABETES MELLITUS ATTENDING PRIMARY DIABETIC CENTER IN SOUTH SHARQIYA
GP Student(s)	Amira Ali Juma Al Shaibi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Type-2 diabetes mellitus represents significant global health concern as there is an emerging recognition of its impact on mental health, particularly depression. Understanding the psychosocial aspects of T2DM is crucial, as they significantly influence overall well-being and quality of life of individuals.
Significance of the Study	Findings from the study can draw attention of healthcare professionals on the prevalence of depression and its potential effect on health-related quality of life and guide the development of targeted interventions and personalized treatment plans.
Aim of the Study	The study examined the level of depression and health-related quality of life among patients with type 2 diabetes attending Diabetes Center.
Methodology	A quantitative non-clinical, cross-sectional investigation involving a population of diabetic type 2 patients visiting the diabetic center are selected by convenience sampling technique. A self-administered questionnaire was used to assess level of depression (PHQ-9) and the EQ-5D-5L, which assessed health-related quality of life.
Overall Outcome	A total of 55 participants showed that the average of depression prevalence was 9.09%, the level of health-related quality of life was 60.3% and the correlation coefficient between PH and EQ-5D was -0.9624 which is a negative significant correlation between depression and health related quality of life among diabetic type 2 patients.
Keywords	<i>depression, health-related quality of life, type-2 diabetes, diabetes center</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE ON PREVENTION OF CENTRAL LINE-ASSOCIATED BLOODSTREAM INFECTION (CLABSI) AMONG ONCOLOGY AND MEDICAL STAFF NURSES AT ROYAL HOSPITAL, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Ilham Mansoor Alfarsi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Central line associated blood stream infection (CLABSI) represents a major threat to patient safety, leading to increased morbidity and mortality rate and burden the cost on health care. Nurses play significant role in preventing these infections through following evidence-based practice guidelines.
Significance of the Study	The results of this research will contribute to enhance the hospital effort in quality management by identifying areas where CLABSI prevention practices can be strengthened.
Aim of the Study	This study explored the relationship between knowledge, attitude, and practice in preventing CLABSI in the medical and oncology units of Royal Hospital, Oman.
Methodology	This is a quantitative, descriptive cross-sectional study of 167 nurses. A self-administered questionnaire, adapting items from multiple literature sources was used to collect data on CLABSI prevention. Ethical approval was obtained from RERAC, Ministry of Health. Descriptive and parametric statistical analysis were done on SPSS software.
Overall Outcome	Overall, nurses' knowledge level was moderate and exhibited positive attitude and good practice toward CLABSI prevention. Years of experience and training significantly influenced practice level. A significant positive correlation between knowledge and practice ($p < 0.001$) and no significant correlation between practice and attitude or between attitude and knowledge was observed.
Keywords	<i>central line associated blood stream infection, knowledge, attitude, practice, CLABSI prevention</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVANT LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG NURSES OF SULTAN QABOOS HOSPITAL, SALALAH
GP Student(s)	Tariq Ramis Salim Jaboob Abdul-Aziz Abdullah Ali-Suliman
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Ability to care for clients that nurses serve can be influenced by the leadership behavior of nurses, as espoused by Greenleaf's (2002) "servant leadership" concept. Association between servant leadership behavior and employees' organizational commitment is a vital theme to study.
Significance of the Study	Study will assist hospital administrators to set a culture where nurses exhibit servant leadership behaviors and a workplace where nurses feel comfortable and committed.
Aim of the Study	To determine relationship between servant leadership and organizational commitment among nurses serving in in-patient departments of Sultan Qaboos Hospital, Salalah.
Methodology	Using a descriptive correlational design, data was collected from nursing staff in Sultan Qaboos Hospital using Servant Leadership Questionnaire-SL7 and the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire. Ethical approval was obtained from Research Ethics Committee of the Ministry of Health.
Overall Outcome	A moderate degree of servant leadership behaviors (M=3.43) was observed among nurses with significant difference between employment position (p=.000) and years of experience (p=.015). Moderate organizational commitment was observed (M=3.03) with significant difference between age groups (p=.000); level of education (p=.018); employment position (p=.000); and years of experience p=.001). A statistically weak, positive correlation between servant leadership and organizational commitment (p=.007) among participants was observed.
Keywords	<i>leadership behaviors, servant leadership behaviors, organizational commitment, nurses, Oman</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	OMANI FAMILY CARE PROVIDERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS OLDER PEOPLE AND THEIR PERCEPTION TOWARDS DAY CARE CENTER FOR ELDERLY PEOPLE IN OMAN
GP Student(s)	Humaid Mohammed Al-Masoudi
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	There was not enough evidence and studies about elderly in Oman. Elderly Care Service program provided in primary health care facilities for all Omani citizens is moving in the right track, however, there are health care needs that are still not met which are related to physical and psychological health, community life, and the settings in which they live.
Significance of the Study	The information from the study will assist in determining feasibility of having elderly day care centers that meet the care needs of elderly population in Omani communities.
Aim of the Study	The study explored the family care providers' attitude towards older people and their perception regarding placing elderly people in a day care center.
Methodology	Descriptive cross-sectional design was used. Convenience sampling method was used to select sample of 89 family care providers from Ibra health center, Ibra hospital, and Sinaw hospital. Self-reported questionnaire containing the Attitude Toward Older People Scale and Perception Towards Day Care Center was used. Ethical approval was obtained. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was then used to analyze the data using descriptive statistics.
Overall Outcome	Findings suggest that family care providers generally have a positive attitude towards older people and recognize the importance of day care centers for elderly. Understanding these attitudes and perceptions towards day care centers for the elderly is crucial for developing effective support systems and services for elderly individuals in Oman.
Keywords	<i>Omani elderly people., caregiver, attitude, perception, family caregiver, day care center</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	FACTORS AFFECTING THE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF PREGNANT WOMEN TOWARD ANTENATAL CARE IN ALMAWALEH HEALTH CENTER, A'SEEB, MUSCAT GOVERNORATE
Student(s)	Kadhiya Al Riyami
Supervisor(s)	Ms. Dulce Racquel M. Javier
Problem Statement	Pregnancy is a biological phenomenon characterized by the implantation and development of a fertilized egg within the uterus, and is accompanied by significant mental and physiological changes. Even in an otherwise typical pregnancy, various issues and complications may arise that pose significant threats to both maternal and fetal health. Every year, over half a million women die due to pregnancy-related causes, with many more suffering from avoidable complications that could be mitigated through proficient antenatal care. Moreover, enhancement of maternal health is pivotal for ensuring the survival and well-being of the fetus.
Significance of the Study	Identifying the relationship between factors influencing attitude and practice toward antenatal care is essential for the nursing and midwifery practice so the proper actions will be taken under consideration. This study is likewise essential for early detection of any pregnancy related problems which need early action to control, treat, prevent and apply the suitable actions. Also, it will reduce the rate of undiagnosed fetal problems and congenital disorders.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to determine factors affecting the attitude and practices of pregnant women toward antenatal care.
Methodology	A quantitative, descriptive, cross-sectional survey design was utilized, involving 100 pregnant women from the ANC of Almwaleh health center, in Muscat. The collection of data was done using self-administered questionnaire directly from the respondents, using convenience sampling technique. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	The finding showed that there are significant association between factors such as age, educational level, occupation and parity, which affect the mothers' attitude and practice toward ANC care. Mothers have positive attitude toward ANC, as 45 % were strongly agreed and agreed that early antenatal booking is good for the pregnancy (mean=1.68). A positive practice toward ANC as 77% visits occurred between 1 to 3 months of pregnancy. Finally, based on the factors examined it is shown that there is a significant association between age, educational level, occupation and gravity, with the examined factors. Concerns such as fear of complications and lack of trust in healthcare teams were identified.
Keywords	<i>pregnancy, knowledge, attitude, antenatal care, antenatal clinic</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURES TO BLOOD AND BLOOD PRODUCTS: ASSESSING KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES AMONG HEALTHCARE PERSONNEL OF THE ACCIDENT AND EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT OF KHOULA HOSPITAL, OMAN
GP Student(s)	Said Mohammed Abdullah Al Rashdi Naif Rabia Ali Al Ghafri
GP Supervisor(s)	Dr. Oscar M. Turingan
Problem Statement	Blood exposure accidents (BEA) remain a significant occupational hazard for healthcare workers, particularly nurses, potentially leading to transmission of blood borne pathogens. Understanding nurses' knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) related to BEA is crucial for developing effective prevention strategies.
Significance of the Study	The results of this study will suggest a positive foundation for Blood exposure accident prevention practices among healthcare personnel.
Aim of the Study	The study aimed to examine healthcare personnel's knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning occupational exposure to blood and blood products at Khoula Hospital A & E Department.
Methodology	A quantitative descriptive correlational design was employed. An online survey assessed the KAP concerning blood and blood product exposure among healthcare personnel working at the Accident and Emergency Department in Khoula Hospital.
Overall Outcome	There was high level of knowledge about BEA among participants (M=2.96,SD±0.18). Additionally, participants showed favorable attitude on BEA prevention (71% with positive views; M=2.58, SD±0.718). Majority (56.6%; M=4.51, SD±0.612) were rated as proficient in BEA prevention practices. A statistically significant associations were identified between age and both attitude towards BEA ($\chi^2 [8, 83]=18.47, p < 0.05$) and level of BEA practices ($\chi^2 [6, 83]=16.3, p=0.012$). However, no significant associations observed between gender, work position, or years of experience with KAP related to BEA prevention. No significant relationships between knowledge and practices, attitude and practices, or knowledge and attitude regarding BEA prevention.
Keywords	<i>occupational exposures, blood products, knowledge, attitude, practice, healthcare personnel, accident and emergency, Oman</i>

Full Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	THE LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF CLIENTS ATTENDING PRIMARY HEALTH CARE FACILITIES IN WILAYAT NIZWA ON THE HEALTH CARE DELIVERY SERVICES IN THE SULTANATE OF OMAN
GP Student(s)	Ahood Mohammed Mubarak Al Nadabi Saeeda Said Hamed Al Rawahi
GP Supervisor(s)	Mr. Phildon Jonar M. Austria
Problem Statement	Health is the cornerstone of a long and enjoyable life. People with health conditions seek health services to sustain health and eventually to improve quality of life. In the Sultanate of Oman, health services are free and various health programs are made available to all. However, client satisfaction to the available services would greatly affect health care utilization and compliance, hence, making it imperative to evaluate if client satisfaction is achieved or not.
Significance of the Study	The findings of this study will help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of healthcare services offered by the Ministry of Health in the Sultanate of Oman which will anchor the creation of effective health programs that will promote and sustain compliance and utilization of free health care services to improve health.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to assess the level of satisfaction of clients attending primary health care facilities in Wilayat Nizwa on the available health care delivery services offered by the Sultanate of Oman and to correlate the relationship between demographics and the satisfaction levels.
Methodology	A quantitative descriptive correlational research design was used. A total of 371 respondents were included applying convenience sampling. All non-Omani who attended and availed of the health services of the centers were excluded. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	The aspects of courtesy, client confidentiality and caring attributes of doctors have merited the highest client satisfaction. Results of correlation indicated that in terms of gender, males tend to report higher satisfaction levels with health care services compared to females. The higher the age, the higher is the level of satisfaction, while the level of education does not significantly affect patient satisfaction.
Keywords	<i>client, satisfaction, health care, primary health facilities</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF CAREGIVERS ON PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION AMONG BED-RIDDEN CLIENTS IN MUSCAT
GP Student(s)	Safiya Saif Said Al-Harthy
GP Supervisor(s)	Mr. Phildon Jonar M. Austria
Problem Statement	Pressure ulcers (PUs) is one among the common health problems affecting debilitated and bed-ridden clients like the older individuals. It is costly and requires extensive treatment and adequate caregiver training to ensure that proper client care is achieved. Lack of knowledge from the caregivers would greatly affect the quality of care and ultimately affecting the client's quality of life.
Significance of the Study	Determining the caregiver's knowledge and attitude on pressure ulcer prevention provides information on the gaps that should be addressed. Result of the study will help yield additional programs and health care initiatives to better improve the quality of care for older individuals.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge and attitude of caregivers on pressure ulcer prevention and to explore the correlation between these two variables.
Methodology	A cross-sectional design was utilized in the study. Out of the 200 caregivers, a total of 145 participated with the exclusion of those with medical background. The sampling technique that was used in the study was convenience sampling. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	The results showed that caregivers of bedridden individuals in Muscat have a moderate level of knowledge ($M = 73.68, SD = 8.36$) regarding pressure ulcers, and had a positive attitude ($M = 2.62, SD = 0.66$) towards preventing pressure ulcers. There was no significant relationship between demographic variables, and caregiver's knowledge, and attitude while there is a weak positive linear relationship between the level of knowledge and the caregiver's attitude level ($r = 0.045, p < 0.05$). The results suggest that educational programs are necessary in improving caregiver's knowledge and attitude toward pressure ulcer prevention.
Keywords	<i>pressure ulcer, caregiver, knowledge, attitude, bedridden</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

College of Health Sciences
School of Nursing

SoN GP SYNOPSIS

GP Title	JOB SATISFACTION AND TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG NURSES WORKING IN EMERGENCY AND IN-PATIENT DEPARTMENTS IN SULTAN QABOOS HOSPITAL, SALALAH
Student(s)	Salma Ramahan Jamaan Bait Nasib
Supervisor(s)	Dr. Jestoni Maniago
Problem Statement	Nursing job satisfaction and turnover intention are pivotal factors that influence patient care quality, organizational performance, and nurse well-being. High turnover rates disrupt care continuity and increase operational costs. Despite this, limited research has comprehensively explored the dynamics between job satisfaction and turnover intention in emergency and in-patient settings.
Significance of the Study	Understanding the correlation between job satisfaction (JS) and turnover intention (TI) is essential for healthcare organizations to enhance nurse retention and mitigate the adverse effects of turnover. This study offers actionable insights to improve nursing staff morale, productivity, and overall satisfaction, ultimately elevating patient care and organizational outcomes.
Aim of the Study	This study aimed to evaluate the levels of job satisfaction and turnover intention among nurses working in emergency and in-patient departments and to explore the correlation between these two variables.
Methodology	A cross-sectional design was employed, targeting 565 nurses with over one year of experience. Exclusion criteria included nurses with less than one year of experience, those on leave or temporary contracts, and expatriates from other institutions. Convenience sampling yielded 172 participants, with data collected via an online survey. IBM SPSS V.20 was used for data analysis.
Overall Outcome	Results revealed a moderately high job satisfaction mean score of 3.62, with the highest satisfaction reported in co-worker relationships (mean: 4.02). Turnover intention was relatively low (mean: 2.1). A weak negative correlation between satisfaction with compensation and turnover intention was significant ($r = -0.193$, $p = 0.011$), while other job satisfaction dimensions showed no significant correlation with turnover intention. The results demonstrate how important compensation-related issues must be addressed in healthcare organizations to reduce employee turnover and promote staff retention. Retention incentives can also be managed and used to recognize and reward long-term service.
Keywords	<i>job satisfaction, turnover intention, nurse retention, emergency and in-patient departments, compensation strategies</i>

Fall Semester
2023-2024

